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ARTÍCULO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

Impacto de la cultura corporativa en el compromiso de los empleados que trabajan en pequeñas y medianas empresas del Delta del Mekong, Vietnam/DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8347151

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Resumen

En el contexto actual de competencia cada vez más evidente entre las empresas, construir y promover los efectos positivos de la cultura corporativa para desarrollar los recursos humanos y retener a los buenos empleados se considera una de las prioridades que deben llevar a cabo las empresas. Para aclarar el impacto de la cultura corporativa en el compromiso de los empleados que trabajan en pequeñas y medianas empresas del delta del Mekong, el estudio realizó una encuesta a 228 empleados de pequeñas y medianas empresas. El autor llevó a cabo la investigación a través de dos fases: investigación cualitativa e investigación cuantitativa. Además, el método de análisis de datos seleccionado por el autor (1) análisis estadístico descriptivo; (2) evaluar la fiabilidad de la escala con el coeficiente Alfa de Cronbach; (3) análisis de correlación; (4) probar la diferencia de medias (5) analizar el modelo de regresión múltiple. Los resultados del análisis muestran que una cultura que fomenta la innovación y el trabajo en equipo, promueve las normas y la responsabilidad social tiene un impacto positivo en el compromiso de los empleados. El artículo ha contribuido teóricamente aportando más pruebas empíricas sobre el papel de la cultura corporativa en la mejora del compromiso de los empleados de las pequeñas y medianas empresas. Además, se sugieren algunas implicaciones de gestión importantes para las pequeñas y medianas empresas en la construcción de la cultura corporativa hacia la mejora del compromiso de los empleados.

Palabras clave: Cultura empresarial; compromiso; empresas; Mekong Delta

Abstract

Impact of corporate culture on the commitment of employees working in small and medium enterprise in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam

In the context of increasingly obvious competition between businesses today, building and promoting the positive effects of corporate culture in order to develop human resources as well as retain good employees is considered one of the priorities that businesses should carry out. To clarify the impact of corporate culture on the commitment of employees working in small and medium-sized enterprises in the Mekong Delta, the study conducted a survey of 228 employees of small and medium-sized enterprises. The author conducted the research through two phases: qualitative research and quantitative research. Besides, the data analysis method selected by the author (1) descriptive statistics analysis; (2) evaluate the reliability of the scale with Cronbach's

Alpha coefficient; (3) correlation analysis; (4) test the mean difference (5) analyze multiple regression model. The results of the analysis show that a culture that encourages innovation and teamwork, promotes standards and social responsibility has a positive impact on employee engagement. The article has contributed theoretically by providing more empirical evidence on the role of corporate culture in improving employee engagement in small and medium enterprises. In addition, some important management implications are suggested for small and medium-sized enterprises in building corporate culture towards improving employee commitment.

Keywords: Corporate culture; commitment; enterprises; Mekong Delta.

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1.- Introduction

The importance of corporate culture to the survival and success of the business is increasingly being realized. Managers are also more concerned with the influence of corporate culture on behavior, attitudes and how members of the organization make their decisions. Corporate culture is gradually recognized as an effective way to attract and retain talented human resources for the organization. On the other hand, human resources are increasingly valued by businesses in the context of the industrial revolution 4.0 and the rapid digital transformation process. In fact, the lack or loss of experienced personnel who are able to apply and master modern technology can cause businesses to pay a significant fee related to new recruitment, retraining or employee rotation. Therefore, managers are always looking for more effective solutions to improve employees' commitment to the organization to ensure the stability of the organization's personnel as well as improving employee productivity.

In Vietnam, small and medium enterprises account for a large proportion. According to the General Statistics Office, by the end of 2022, there are nearly 54,000 small and medium enterprises operating in the Mekong Delta, accounting for about 97% of the total number of businesses operating in the region. Small and medium enterprises contribute to the region's GDP on average about 70%/year and solve for 51.0% of labor in the enterprise sector in general. Increasing the level of employee commitment to the organization is a big challenge for managers, especially in the wake of the Covid-19 pandemic when small and medium-sized businesses are accelerating the recovery process, looking for effective ways to attract employees back to work and retain them in the future. At this time, corporate culture is more and more focused not only to improve the competitiveness of the business but also to help improve work results and employee commitment.

In domestic and foreign studies, corporate culture and employee commitment are topics that attract the attention of many scholars with diverse approaches. However, most of the studies focus on the relationship between corporate culture and business results of enterprises such as revenue, profit, productivity, but have not mentioned much about the link between values. organizational culture with aspects of psychology, attitude and behavior of employees. Several studies have shown that corporate culture has a positive impact on employee commitment to the organization, making them loyal to the organization and willing to contribute more at work (Herminingsih, 2015). Changes in corporate culture also have an impact on employee engagement levels with the organization. Meanwhile, domestic studies on the influence of corporate culture on employee commitment are relatively limited, the research scope is still limited, limited to one or a group of small enterprises (Nguyen Nam Hai, 2019).

From the important role of corporate culture in promoting employee engagement in the current context and the lack of further research on this topic, the article focuses on answering two questions: (1) How does corporate culture affect employee engagement? (2) Is this impact different between the group of employees who have direct and indirect contact with customers? To clarify this issue, the article first summarizes some important theoretical bases on the influence of corporate culture on employee commitment to the organization. Next, the author proposes an analytical model based on domestic and foreign studies on this topic. After presenting the research method, the article analyzes in detail the obtained research results in order to draw conclusions about the role of corporate culture with employee commitment. On that basis propose implications for the managers of small and medium enterprises in the Mekong Delta.

2.- Theoretical basis and research model

2.1. Theoretical basis

2.1.1. Corporate culture

With an important role in improving organizational business results, corporate culture has attracted the attention of academics and executives for more than half a century. However, up to now, corporate culture has not been uniformly defined. Corporate culture is understood as a set of basic values, beliefs and assumptions that members of an organization have discovered and developed in the process of adapting to internal and external problems of the organization, determining how members perceive, think, and respond appropriately when problems arise (Schneider et al., 2017). In other words, corporate culture consists of the values shared by the members of the organization and the underlying assumptions that explain the reasons for the activities the organization is doing and issues of interest to the organization. Corporate culture is the product created by members who work together for a long time at an organization, creating a distinctive feature that distinguishes this business from other businesses.

To evaluate corporate culture, researchers and well-known consulting organizations in the world have proposed many different tools and scales. In academic research alone, more than 70 tools have been and are being used, corresponding to which dozens of different aspects of corporate culture have been analyzed. In small and medium enterprises, some authors have proposed a separate corporate culture scale to reflect specific aspects (Tepeci & Barlett, 2002). The diversity in definitions and scales has posed a big challenge for scholars in choosing the right approaches and tools when researching on this topic.

2.1.2. Employee commitment to the organization

Employee commitment is a new topic that has been mentioned a lot in research on corporate governance and organizational psychology since the beginning of the 21st century. Research by Kahn (1990) suggests that people will put their own cognitive, emotional, and physical into the work they perform in the workplace to varying degrees. Stemming from that background, Saks (2006) defined employee engagement as the degree to which an employee is psychologically present in a particular organizational role. According to this study, the author made a clear distinction between employee commitment to work and employee commitment to the organization. This is an important step forward that allows to explore more deeply the aspects of commitment because before that, many documents used different terms such as employee commitment, commitment. commitment to work... but they only show the aspect of commitment to employees' behavior towards the jobs they are performing.

Unlike the commitment to work, employee commitment to the organization is understood as the desire to continue to stay in the organization as a member of the organization, the willingness to comply with the values of the organization and strives to fulfill its job role for the benefit of the whole organization (Saks, 2006). Employees who are committed to the organization will pay more attention to the performance of their role in the organization, devote more energy to their work, and achieve higher work performance (Maslach et al. events, 2001). They are also optimistic, highly focused on work, enthusiastic and willing to try harder to contribute to the success of the organization in the future (Jose and Mampilly, 2012).

Several empirical studies have shown that employee commitment to the organization has an impact on the turnover rate, turnover, labor productivity, and job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior (Buil et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2017). In addition, a high level of employee engagement promotes creativity and innovation in the business and is positively related to customer satisfaction. It can be seen that employees with long-term commitment to the organization need to be recognized as a strategic asset of the enterprise and receive more attention from managers (Nutov and Hazzan, 2014).

2.1.3. The influence of corporate culture on employee commitment

More than a decade ago, empirical studies have just begun to be conducted more to examine the relationship between corporate culture and employee commitment to the organization, although there have been some theoretical studies on this topic before. Research by Martin and Hetrick (2006) shows that corporate culture towards employee engagement can make it easier for businesses to attract and retain talented employees. Not only that, businesses that build a culture where employees are closely attached to the organization will achieve better financial results than other businesses in the same industry.

Several studies at specific companies have shown a strong correlation between aspects of corporate culture and employee engagement levels (Barbars, 2018). Enterprises have a culture that values the value of employees, respects the interests of employees and efforts to build strong relationships among members of the organization often recognize a higher level of employee commitment and employees are also willing to put more effort to contribute to the achievement of the common goals of the organization.

Besides the traditional factors that are often studied such as organizational processes, compensation and benefits, the leadership of superiors, corporate culture is gradually focused as a fundamental factor affecting employee commitment. Enterprises with a positive culture, promoting innovation, encouraging internal communication and emphasizing integrity will create strong motivation for employees even if the company does not offer too many financial rewards to employees (Najeemdeen et al., 2018).

In addition, research by Lockwood (2007) describes a meaningful corporate culture that needs to be built and strengthened to make employees more committed to the organization. Accordingly, corporate culture should promote employee contributions, encourage more challenging tasks for employees, towards creativity and create opportunities for employees to develop their own capabilities. In particular, the interaction and mutual support between colleagues in the organization and the close connection with customers are also important aspects of corporate culture that affect employee commitment.

In general, current studies mainly analyze the impact of corporate culture and employee commitment based on organizational psychology theories. The few empirical studies on this effect have only focused on a specific type of culture without fully examining the impact of different cultural dimensions on employee commitment. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct more empirical studies on the impact of corporate culture on employee commitment, especially looking specifically at small and medium-sized enterprises in the Mekong Delta with urgency.

3. Research models

Based on an overview of studies on corporate culture and employee engagement in general and documents on corporate culture in small and medium enterprises in particular, The OCP organizational culture analysis framework (Tepeci & Barlett, 2002) allows to approach corporate culture from the perspective of cultural values, thereby allowing the simultaneous study of diverse cultural aspects in organizations and highlight the typical values of small and medium enterprises. Accordingly, corporate culture is considered in five aspects: encouraging innovation, encouraging teamwork, promoting standards, being results-oriented, and promoting social responsibility. The relationship between corporate culture and employee commitment to the organization is explained based on social exchange theory (Saks, 2006). Accordingly, when the corporate culture shows the organization's interest and focus on employees, they will feel that the organization is bringing benefits to them, since then they want to return commensurate values to the organization through greater commitment and dedication to the organization. Therefore, the article proposes the following hypotheses:

H1a: Culture encourages innovation has a positive effect on employee commitment to the organization.

H1b: Culture encourages teamwork has a positive effect on employee commitment to the organization.

H1c: Culture upholds standards has a positive effect on employee commitment to the organization.

H1d: Results-oriented culture has a positive effect on employee commitment to the organization.

H1e: Culture upholding social responsibility has a positive effect on employee commitment to the organization.

H2: The level of impact of corporate culture on employees' commitment to the organization is different between the two groups (employees in contact with and without direct contact with customers). The research model is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1.
Author's proposed research model

4. RESEARCH METHODS

4.1. Scale development

The scales used in the study were built based on an overview of studies on corporate culture and employee commitment. The scale was then adjusted and supplemented to suit the research context of small and medium enterprises in the Mekong Delta, based on the results of in-depth interviews with 5 experts from universities majoring in Economics, who have a deep understanding of corporate culture, commitment of employees and management activities of small and medium enterprises. The corporate culture scale is built based on the OCP corporate culture theory of Tepeci & Barlett (2002) and the normative culture scale of Bradley et al (2006).

Table 1
Scale of research concepts

Encode	Research concept	Number of observed variables	Reference source
ST	Culture encourages innovation	5	Tepeci & Barlett (2002); Expert discussion
LN	Culture encourages teamwork	5	Tepeci & Barlett (2002); Expert discussion
QC	Culture upholds standards	5	Bradley và cộng sự (2006); Expert discussion
KQ	Results-oriented culture	5	Tepeci & Barlett (2002); Expert discussion
XH	Culture upholding social responsibility	5	Tepeci & Barlett (2002); Expert discussion
GB	Employee commitment to the organization	7	Saks (2006); Expert discussion

Source: Compiled by the author's research

4.2. Research stages

4.2.1. Qualitative research

At the preliminary research stage, the author uses qualitative research methods with target group discussion techniques. Specifically: the author uses convenient sampling method, selects 10 employees and 10 managers who are leaders of enterprises located in provinces and regions in the Mekong Delta. All interviews were in the form of face-to-face interviews with a duration of 30 to 60 minutes, with an average of 45 minutes. Interview period is from March 2023 to April 2023. Objectives of the target group interview are the staff to evaluate and edit the content of observations and models, research hypotheses, how to measure variables and the results of the model.

Objectives of the target group interview are managers to find out, their views on the impact of corporate culture on employee commitment in their business. Also, investigate their level of understanding and contribution to the observations in the research scale.

4.2.2. Quantitative research

At the quantitative research stage, the author uses the non-probability sampling method, which is convenience sampling, which is applied when implementing sampling, whereby a list of small and medium-sized enterprises classified according to their business lines is used to conduct the survey. Survey subjects are employees of small and medium-sized enterprises in the Mekong Delta by gender, age, qualifications and job position, with at least 2 years of seniority at the enterprise, including including those who work directly and not directly with customers in different parts of the enterprise in order to verify the accuracy and suitability of the model, assess the reliability of the scale, variables, observations include and discard inappropriate indicators. Data were collected by distributing questionnaires to a direct survey for the period from May 1, 2023 to June 1, 2023, with an expected sample size of 250 employees.

4.3. Data analysis

- Test the reliability of the scale and descriptive statistics: Using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient to evaluate the quality of the construction scale. The scale is evaluated as good quality when: (1) Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of the population is greater than 0.6; and (2) The correlation coefficient - the sum of the observed variables is greater than 0.3 (Corrected Item - Total Corelation) (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994).
- Exploratory factor analysis (EFA)
- Correlation analysis
- Test for mean difference
- Analysis of regression model to evaluate the impact of corporate culture on employee commitment in small and medium enterprises in the Mekong Delta.

5. RESEARCH RESULTS

5.1. Research sample information

The research sample was selected by the non-probability sampling method, which is convenient sampling, stratified relatively according to provinces and localities in order to increase the representativeness of the research sample including Can Tho City, Dong Thap province, Vinh Long province, An Giang province, Kien Giang province, Tien Giang province and classified according to the type of business line of the enterprise, gender, age, qualification and job position. The investigation unit in the study is defined as an employee in small and medium-sized enterprises and has at least 2 years of seniority

working at the enterprise, including those who work directly and not directly with customers in different parts of the business.

Table 2.
Distribution of the research sample

Research sample structure		Number of survey samples	Number of samples collected	Ratio %
Local investigation	Can Tho City	50	45	20.0
	Dong Thap province	50	47	20.5
	Vinh Long province	40	37	16.1
	An Giang province	40	36	15.7
	Kien Giang province	40	37	16.1
	Tien Giang province	30	26	11.6
Business	Agriculture forestry seafood	85	76	33.6
	Industry, Build	85	79	34.4
	Commerce, service	80	73	32.0
Gender	Male	98	89	38,7
	Female	152	139	61,3
Age	Under 25 years old	73	67	29,4
	25-35 years old	66	60	26,5
	35-45 years old	61	56	24,5
	Over 45 years old	50	45	19,6
Level	High School	15	9	5,8
	College	44	40	17,8
	University	156	142	62,5
	After university	35	37	13,9
Job position	Direct contact with customers	136	124	54,3
	No direct contact with customers	114	104	45,7
Total		250	228	100

Source: Compiled by the author's research

From 250 questionnaires sent initially, the author obtained 232 survey questionnaires with a response rate of 92.8%. After removing invalid votes, 228 survey questionnaires were included in the analysis. Some characteristics of the study sample are summarized in Table 2. The research sample is mainly female, accounting for more than 60% and has a relatively young age with more than 50% of the surveyed people under 35 years old. Most of the staff are at university or above. The percentage of respondents who are working in direct and non-customer positions is about the same. To ensure the reliability and accuracy of the scale, the collected data is tested based on Cronbach's Alpha coefficient and EFA exploratory factor analysis. The analysis coefficients all confirm that the scale has an appropriate level of reliability. The data was then entered into SPSS 22 software to test the scale, analyze descriptive statistics, test mean differences, analyze correlation and regression to test the research hypotheses.

5.2. Evaluate the reliability of the scale

The results of descriptive statistical analysis show that small and medium-sized enterprises have built a culture emphasizing innovation, teamwork, results orientation and social responsibility with an average score of 3, 74 to 3.85. The aspect of culture that emphasizes standards has not been really focused with an average value of less than 3. The level of employee commitment to the organization is above average with a value of 3.53. All 6 scales are reliable with Cronbach's Alpha coefficients greater than 0.6, total correlation coefficients are greater than 0.3, ensuring the reliability of the scale (Hair et al. 2009).

Table 3.

Results of testing the reliability of the scale and descriptive statistics

Variable	Symbol	Coefficient Cronbach's Alpha	Value medium	Standard deviation
Culture encourages innovation	ST	0.810	3,85	0,69
Culture encourages teamwork	LN	0.840	3,78	0,79
Culture upholds standards	QC	0.850	2,76	0,86
Results-oriented culture	KQ	0.840	3,74	0,74
Culture upholding social responsibility	XH	0.820	3,77	0,75
Employee commitment to the organization	GB	0.890	3,53	0,60

Source: Compiled by the author's research

5.3. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA)

Exploratory factor analysis using Varimax rotation was conducted with 5 independent variables and 1 dependent variable to test the relationship between variables in the same scale. For the two analyzes, the KMO coefficients both reach values greater than 0.5, the Barlett test coefficient has a significance level of 0.00, the total variance extracted is greater than 50%, proving that the factor analysis is appropriate. and observed variables are correlated with each other in the factor. The factor loading coefficients of all observed variables are greater than 0.5, the observed variables of the dependent variable converge on one variable. These indexes show the unidirectionality of the scale, ensure the convergence of the observed variables, and the scale is qualified to conduct correlation and regression analysis.

5.4. Correlation analysis

The results of the correlation analysis between factors show that employees' commitment to the organization is correlated with aspects of corporate culture at the significance level of 0.01. In which, culture that promotes social responsibility and encourages innovation has the strongest correlation with employee engagement with the correlation coefficient greater than 0.5. Results-oriented culture has the lowest correlation coefficient with employee engagement at 0.387. The five dimensions of corporate culture were moderately correlated with each other, with the exception of the innovation-driven culture and the results-oriented culture that were not significantly correlated.

Table 4.
Correlation analysis results

	GB	ST	LN	QC	KQ	XH
Employee commitment to the organization	1	0,541**	0,466**	0,497**	0,386**	0,566**
Culture encourages innovation		1	0,214**	0,228**	0,119**	0,453**
Culture encourages teamwork			1	0,318**	0,602**	0,338**
Culture upholds standards				1	0,322**	0,371**
Results-oriented culture					1	0,318**
Culture upholding social responsibility						1

**Significant correlation at 0.01 (2-tailed) level

Source: Data analysis results

5.5. Test for mean difference

Independent sample T-test was conducted to determine the average difference in the perceived level of corporate culture and the employee's commitment to the organization between whether groups of employees occupy different positions in the organization. Levene test results with a significance value less than 0.05 indicate the difference in the level of employee commitment to the organization between two groups of employees in contact with and without direct contact with customers. On the other hand, there is a difference in the perception of the two groups of employees about three aspects of corporate culture, including a culture that promotes teamwork, respects standards, and promotes social responsibility.

Table 5.
Results of testing the mean difference between two groups of employees

	Employees in direct contact with customers	Employees do not have direct contact with customers	Levene's Test for equality of variances		T-test for equality of means		
			F	Sig.	t	Df	Sig. (2- tailed)
Culture encourages innovation	3,66	3,86	6,181	0,013	-1,861	185	0,063
					-1,886	181,2	0,060
Culture encourages teamwork	3,63	3,96	8,941	0,002	-2,862	185	0,004
					-2,915	174,9	0,003
Culture upholds standards	2,63	2,90	2,791	0,095	-2,158	185	0,031
					-2,175	184,6	0,030
Results-oriented culture	3,65	3,84	1,930	0,165	-1,774	185	0,077
					-1,790	184,1	0,074
Culture upholding social responsibility	3,64	3,92	1,479	0,224	-2,641	185	0,008
					-2,655	184,9	0,008
Employee commitment to the organization	3,30	3,79	2,682	0,102	-6,133	185	0,000
					-6,179	184,7	0,000

Source: Data analysis results

5.6. Analysis of regression model

The results of the regression analysis with the entire sample allow to assess the impact of corporate cultural aspects on employee commitment. For the three regression models, the results of the analysis of variance are in agreement with the significance level of 0.00. The VIF variance magnification factors are all less than 2, ensuring no multicollinearity. First, the adjusted R-squared coefficient of 0.54 shows that all five aspects of corporate culture explain more than 50% of the variation in employee engagement. Specifically, the culture that encourages innovation has the greatest influence, followed by a culture that promotes standards, promotes social responsibility, and encourages teamwork. Results-oriented culture has no impact on employee commitment.

Next, two regression models were analyzed for the two groups of respondents to show the difference in the influence of cultural aspects on employee commitment. For the group of employees who have direct contact with customers, cultural aspects of the company explain more than 70% of the variation in commitment levels. Meanwhile, this rate in the group of employees who do not contact customers is only nearly 30%. In both groups of employees, the results-oriented culture had no significant impact on commitment. Particularly for the group of employees who do not have direct contact with customers, only the culture that encourages innovation and the culture that values standards has an impact on commitment.

In general, with the results of correlation analysis, difference test and multivariable regression analysis, hypotheses H1a, H1b, H1c, H1e and H2 are accepted. In other words, a culture that encourages innovation, encourages teamwork, promotes ethics and social responsibility has a positive impact on employee commitment to the organization and this impact is differences among employees in different positions in the organization.

Table 6.
Results of Regression Analysis

	Overall sample		Contact staff group direct customer		Non-contact staff group direct customer	
	Normalization coefficient	Level of significance	Normaliza tion coefficient	Level of significa nce	Normaliza tion coefficient	Level of significa nce
R ² correction	0,541		0,702		0,271	
Sig	0,000		0,000		0,000	
Culture encourages innovation	0,32	0,00	0,31	0,00	0,33	0,00
Culture encourages teamwork	0,18	0,00	0,22	0,00	0,05	0,60
Culture upholds standards	0,24	0,00	0,27	0,00	0,18	0,04
Results-oriented culture	0,07	0,22	0,05	0,44	0,13	0,18
Culture upholding social responsibility	0,23	0,00	0,32	0,00	0,09	0,31

Source: Data analysis results

6. DISCUSSION AND GOVERNANCE IMPLICATIONS

6.1. Discussing research results

From the research results obtained, the article proposes a suitable research model and provides more empirical evidence on the impact of corporate culture on employee commitment to the organization. On the one hand, research has clarified the impact of different aspects of corporate culture on employee engagement levels. Accordingly, businesses build a culture that encourages innovation, teamwork and social responsibility through listening to employees' opinions, creating a supportive working environment and focusing on the interests of each individual will make employees more committed to the organization. This result is similar to previous studies of Johnson et al

(2018) when emphasizing that a work culture that gives employees the opportunity to learn, create and support the work team will improve satisfaction, employee commitment and engagement. In addition, the culture of not being too rigidly defined is a characteristic aspect of the culture of small and medium enterprises. The results of the analysis show that the aspect of culture that promotes standards is not clearly recognized in enterprises, but has a significant impact on commitment. Strengthening management policies, regulations and procedures at work can make employees feel tightly controlled by the business but help them do their jobs more smoothly and efficiently, thereby achieving higher results at work and more connected with the organization.

On the other hand, research has shown differences in the impact of corporate culture on commitment among employees in different job positions. In small and medium enterprises, depending on the characteristics of the work they are doing, employees may have different views on the corporate culture, thereby having different levels of commitment. Employees who provide direct service to customers such as customer service staff, sales staff, are those who perform complex jobs, requires the adjustment of behavior and attitudes in accordance with the cultural norms of the enterprise, so their relationship with the organization is somewhat closer. The level of commitment of employees who do not have direct contact with customers, such as staff in the administrative and human resources departments, in the financial planning department, is less affected by aspects of corporate culture. This result reinforces the conclusion of Copus et al (2019) when comparing jobs that are in frequent contact with customers that require employees to have a clear understanding and attitude, behavior in accordance with corporate cultural values, thereby making them gradually integrate more deeply into the organization and commit to a long-term commitment to the business.

6.2. Management Implications

Based on the analysis results, the article offers some implications for the managers of small and medium-sized enterprises in building corporate culture to promote employee commitment. First of all, businesses need to focus on encouraging teamwork, empowering employees, accepting risks, employees' failures, listen to their new ideas to create an environment that makes them more comfortable and willing to give more. Next, small and medium-sized enterprises need to standardize their working processes in order to maintain an appropriate level of flexibility and avoid cumbersome procedures to facilitate employees in the working process. More importantly in the context of the current economic downturn, small and medium enterprises need to pay more attention to corporate social responsibility, especially focusing on the benefits of employees even if they have to cut their working hours or work remotely to make them feel secure to work for the organization long after the economy stabilizes. In addition, with employees who have direct contact with customers, playing an important role in small and medium-

sized businesses as the image representative, conveying the organization's cultural values to customers, businesses need to increase training so that they understand and share those values, and make them feel part of the success of the organization and want to be with the organization in the long term. For employees who do not have direct contact with customers but are often present at the organization, businesses need to strengthen group bonding activities and remind them of the common values of the organization.

7. CONCLUSIONS

Corporate culture is not only an invaluable asset that sets a business apart, but it is also the key to attracting and retaining talented employees to stay with the organization. Based on data collected from 228 employees of small and medium enterprises in the Mekong Delta, research has elucidated the important role of corporate culture in promoting employee commitment to the organization. Through the construction and development of specific cultural values, small and medium enterprises can strengthen the connection between employees and the organization, thereby making them more willing to put in effort and contribute more to the overall success of the organization.

The study still has some limitations when it only analyzes businesses across a geographical area and uses a measure of corporate culture based on employee evaluation. Future studies may expand the sample size and research scope to exploit differences in corporate culture between different fields. In addition, in order to study corporate culture and employee commitment more comprehensively, subsequent studies may incorporate more qualitative research methods such as in-depth interviews or group discussions.

Bibliographic references

- Allen, N. and J Meyer (2016), "The measurement and antecedents of affective, continuance, and normative commitment to the organization". **Journal of Occupational Psychology**, v. 63, pp. 1-18.
- AnithaJ. and Farida B. N, (2016). "Role of Organisational Culture and Employee Commitment in Employee Retention". **International Journal of Asian School of Business Management**, 10, pp. 17-28.
- Barbars, A. (2018). "Interaction between organizational culture and work engagement in the information and communication technology sector in Latvia". **Journal of Business Management**, 4(2), pp. 84-100.

- Bradley, R.V., Pridmore, J.L., Byrd, T.A. (2006). "Information systems success in the context of different corporate cultural types: an empirical investigation". **Journal of Management Information Systems**, 23 (2), pp. 267-294.
- Chow, C.W., Harrison, G.L., McKinnon, J.L., & Wu, A (2011). **Organizational Culture: Association with Affective Commitment, Job Satisfaction, Propensity to Remain and Information Sharing in a Chinese Cultural Context**. CIBER Working paper. San Diego State University.
- Copus, L., Sajgalikova, H. & Wojca, E (2019). "Organizational culture and its motivational potential in manufacturing industry: Subculture perspective". **Procedia Manufacturing**, 32, pp. 360-367.
- Ezekiel S. N. and Darius N. I., (2012). "The Influence of Corporate Culture on Employee Commitment to the Organization". **International Journal of Business and Management**, 7, pp. 22-31.
- Herminingsih, A. (2015). "Building employees, engagement through leadership, human resources management practices and organizational culture". **Journal of Business and Economics**, 6(9), pp. 1613- 1620.
- Huynh Thi Thu Thanh (2013). "Factors affecting employees' attitudes and tendency to leave when the organization changes". **Economic Development Journal**, no. 278, pp. 13-25.
- Heye, Dennie (2016) **Creativity and Innovation: Two key characteristics of successful 21st century information professional**. Business Information Review. SAGE Publications, London.
- Johnson, A., Nguyen, H., Groth, M., & White, L. (2018). "Workplace aggression and organisational effectiveness: The mediating role of employee engagement". **Australian Journal of Management**, 43(4), pp. 614-631.
- Lockwood NR (2007). "Leveraging employee engagement for competitive advantage: HR's strategic role". **Society for Human Resource Management Quarterly**, 1/4.
- Maslach, C., Schaufeli, W.B. and Leiter, M.P. (2001). "Job burnout". **Annual Review of Psychology**, 52(1), pp. 397-422.
- Najeemdeen, I.S., Abidemi, B.T., Rahmat, F.D. & Bulus, B.D. (2018). "Perceived Organizational Culture and Perceived Organizational Support on Work Engagement". **Academic Journal of Economic Studies**, 3, pp. 199-208.

- Nguyen Nam Hai (2019). **The relationship between organizational culture, job engagement and employee performance in Vietnamese information technology enterprises**, PhD Thesis, National Economics University.
- Osibanjo O.A. and Adeniji A., (2013). "Impact of Organizational Culture on Human Resource Practices: A Study of Selected Nigerian Private Universities". **Journal of Competitiveness**, 5, pp. 115-133.
- Phan Quoc Viet, Nguyen Le Anh and Nguyen Huy Hoang (2017). **Corporate culture and competitiveness**, quoted in the book Improving the competitiveness of Vietnamese enterprises in WTO integration, Vietnam Chamber of Commerce and Industry.
- Saks, A.M. (2006). "Antecedents and consequences of employee engagement". **Journal of Managerial Psychology**, 21 (7), pp. 600-619.
- Schneider, B., Gonzalez-Roma, V., Ostroff, C., & West, M. A. (2017). "Organizational Climate and Culture: Reflections on the History of the Constructs in JAP". **Journal of Applied Psychology**, 102(3), pp. 468-482.
- Song, H.J., Hun Lim, D., Gu Kang, I. and Kim, W. (2014). "Team performance in learning organizations: mediating effect of employee engagement". **The Learning Organization**, 21(5), pp. 290-309.
- Syed M. A. et al, (2012). "The Impact of Organizational Culture on the Organizational Commitment: A Study of Faculty Members of Private Sector Universities of Pakistan". **Interdisciplinary Journal of contemporary research in business**, 5, pp. 92-101.
- Syed Z.R. et al, (2011). **Effects of Organizational Culture on Psychology of Employee Commitment**, IEEE, pp. 2049-2053.
- Tepeci, M., & Bartlett, A. L. (2002). "The hospitality industry culture profile: A measure of individual values, organizational culture, and person-organization fit as predictors of job satisfaction and behavioral intentions". **International Journal of Hospitality Management**, 21, pp. 151-170.
- Tran Kim Dung (2015). "Measurement of job satisfaction in Vietnamese conditions". **Journal of Science and Technology Development**, Vietnam National University, Ho Chi Minh City.
- Truong Hoang Lam and Do Thi Thanh Vinh (2012). "The influence of company culture on employee commitment: The case of information system company FPT". **Economic and Development Magazine**, No. 185, pp. 119-127.

- Recardo, R., & Jolly, J. (2015). **Organizational Culture and Teams**, S.A.M Advanced Management Journal.
- Vu Thanh Tu Anh & Nguyen Phuong Lam (2022). **Mekong Delta Annual Economic Report**. VCCI Can Tho & Fulbright.
- Xiaoming C., (2012). "A Literature Review on Organization Culture and Corporate Performance". **International Journal of Business Administration**, 2, pp. 28-37.
- Zhang, Y., Guo, Y., & Newman, A. (2017). "Identity judgements, work engagement and organizational citizenship behavior: The mediating effects based on group engagement model". **Tourism Management**, 61, pp. 190-197.